

СТРУКТУРА ПРЕМОРБІДНОЇ ПАТОЛОГІЇ ПРИ КОРОНАВІРУСНІЙ ХВОРОБИ COVID-19

STRUCTURE OF PREMORBID PATHOLOGY IN CORONAVIRUS DISEASE COVID-19

С. В. Магійович, Є. Я Склярів

S. Mahiiovych, E. Sklyarov

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3934-0523>

Науковий керівник: д. мед. н. професор **Склярів Є. Я.**

Scientific supervisor: Doctor of Medical Science, Professor **E. Sklyarov**

Львівський національний медичний університет імені Данила Галицького

Кафедра терапії №1, медичної діагностики та гематології та
трансфузіології ФПДО

м. Львів, Україна

Danylo Halytsky Lviv National Medical University

Department of Therapy №1, medical diagnostics and hematology and
transfusiology Faculty of postgraduate education

Lviv, Ukraine

e-mail: solka.chekh@gmail.com

Introduction. On March 11, 2020, the WHO declared an outbreak of a new disease caused by the virus SARS-CoV-2 a global pandemic. The clinical course of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) varies from asymptomatic to severe and critical, leading to death. Concomitant pathologies are among the risk factors for severe coronavirus disease.

Objective: To determine the structure of premorbid pathology in hospitalized patients with coronavirus disease with lung damage.

Materials and methods. The study included 243 hospitalized patients with coronavirus disease and lung lesions who were hospitalized at the Kyiv City Medical Center. The diagnosis of coronavirus disease was verified by polymerase chain reaction, and lung damage was confirmed by radiological methods (radioscopy or computed tomography of the chest).

Research results. It was established that among the hospitalized patients with coronavirus infection and lung damage, cardiovascular pathology, type 2 diabetes mellitus and complications were the main background diseases. Thus, 70% of patients with COVID-19 were diagnosed with hypertension, 44.9% with coronary heart disease associated with hypertension, and 22.2% with heart failure. Diabetics accounted for 32% of all patients. Among other concomitant pathologies can be identified CKD - 10%, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease - 8%. It should also be noted that 18.9% of patients admitted with pulmonary lesions showed anemia.

Conclusion. Studies have shown a significant predominance of cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes in the structure of premorbid pathologies in patients with COVID-19.